

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

PRODUCTION OF HYDROGEN BY PHOTOCATALYTIC ORGANIC SUBSTANCE DECOMPOSITION USING CHROMIUM-CONTAINING CERAMET COMPOSITES UNDER THE UV AND VISIBLE IRRADIATION

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Abstract

The phase composition and morphological features of metal-ceramic composites synthesized by self-propagating synthesis from the ferrosilicon aluminum alloy (FSA), silicon-aluminum, ferroboration (FB) and ferrovanadium (FV) powders with the addition of modifiers (shungite, titanium metal) have been investigated. The optical properties of the composites were studied, and the band gap values of the semiconductors included in the ceramic matrix were determined from the electronic absorption spectra. The efficiency of the process of generating hydrogen from solutions of "sacrificial" reagents (carboxylic acids, hydrazine, sucrose) was assessed depending on their concentration and H₂O₂ concentration, dye addition, and phase composition of the composites. It has been shown that the generation of hydrogen from "sacrificial" reagents occurs as a result of a combination of heterogeneous and homogeneous photocatalysis. The highest productivity of hydrogen evolution (~830 μmol·g⁻¹·h⁻¹) was achieved from solutions of oxalic and malic acids.

Keywords: metal-ceramic composites, semiconductors, heterogeneous photocatalysis, homogeneous photocatalysis, hydrogen generation, sacrificial reagents

Introduction

One of the most significant issue in photocatalytic hydrogen generation is the low efficiency such processes. It mostly regards with new H₂ production technology, difficulties in the industrial sailing of the "laboratory approaches" and the common low quantum yield of using transition metals composites. On the one hand, the half-reaction limitations of oxidation of the "sacrificial" reagent and the reduction of hydrogen require an increase in the band gap. On the other hand, catalysts will work most efficiently by absorbing light over a wider region, which requires a decrease in the band gap. At the present time a less part of semiconductors is able to catalyze both Red-Ox half-reactions and work in a wider light region simultaneously. Therefore, there are plenty of approaches to shift composite photocatalytic activity in visible light region in order to use sun irradiation.

One of the most common approaches is to generate hydrogen from organic pollutants and simultaneously degrade them. In this regard, Fe-containing ceramic composites doped by semiconductor compounds are attractive due to their efficiency and economic benefits. They generate in a solution in accelerate reagent (H₂O₂, H₂C₂O₄) oxidation systems (photo-Fenton, ferrioxalate) and provide the conditions for combined the both homogeneous and heterogeneous catalytic interactions. We have found the composite photocatalytic activity (Fe-BN, Fe-Si₃N₄, Fe-Si₃Al₃O₃N₅-Si₃N₄) obtained by autowave combustion of ferroalloys in an atmosphere of gaseous nitrogen using the method of self-

propagating high-temperature synthesis (SHS) [1]. The additions of precursors, modifiers and active components into the reaction mixture made it possible to increase the content of metallic Fe in composites, improve their structural properties, and also achieve high dispersion of active components over the surface [2-4].

In this work, a comparative assessment of the performance of composites in the production of H₂ from organic substances under the influence of UV and visible irradiation was carried out. Five semiconductor composites synthesized by the environmentally friendly SHS method from industrial waste were studied. SiC and TiN composites were obtained by modifying the ceramic matrix of samples based on aluminum nitride and sialon with semiconductor phases of BN and VN in order to improve photocatalytic characteristics and shift light absorption to the visible region.

Synthesis and characterization of composites

In the synthesis of composites based on aluminum nitride, boron and vanadium were used the ferrosilicon aluminum alloy (FSA), silicon-aluminum, ferroboration (FB) and ferrovanadium (FV) powders. For the synthesis, polydisperse powders FSA, FB and FV with a particle size of less than 100-300 microns were used. Before SV synthesis, the initial powders were dried in a vacuum oven at a temperature of 150-200 °C to remove moisture and volatile impurities. Mixing of ferroalloy powders with additives was carried out in dry form mechanically (drum mixer with a volume of 0.5 l). The purity of the nitrogen in the atmosphere of which the combustion took place was 99.9%. The equipments and

combustion process for the synthesis of composites is described in our previous work [5].

The phase composition of the composites was determined using the XRD method on an XRD 6000 diffractometer (Cu-K α radiation, in the 2θ range from 10° to 120°). The SiN-SiC, TiN and SiAlON composites were obtained by nitriding ferrosilicoaluminum (FSA), and the SiN-SiC sample was synthesized with the addition of a modifier - shungite (53-58% SiO₂, 30% C), TiN - with the addition of titanium metal. Optical properties were studied using a Thermo Scientific Evolution 600 UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, USA). The spectra were recorded relative to the MgO standard. The recorded diffuse reflectance spectra of the composites were converted to absorption spectra using the Kubelka-Munk function (1):

$$F = \frac{(1-R)^2}{2R}, \text{ where } R \text{ is the diffuse reflection coefficient} \quad (1)$$

The band gap of the composites was worked out from the intersection of the absorption line tangent with an E_v energy axes. For this purpose, the absorption spectra were converted into a function of the absorption coefficient $(F(R) \cdot E)^n$ depended on the photon energy $h\nu$ with value n $(F(R) \cdot E)^2 = f(h\nu)$ for direct band gaps and $(F(R) \cdot E)^{1/2} = f(h\nu)$ for indirect electron band gaps. Extrapolation of the linear parts of the corresponding dependencies to the $h\nu$ axis gives the E_g of the composites.

The active sites on the surface of the composites were studied by the indicator method of Hammett and Tanabe with spectrophotometric indication.

Methodology of the photocatalytic experiment

A sample of the composite 200 mg was placed in a quartz reactor (100 ml) with 20 ml of a model solution of the "sacrificial" reagent, then 0.2 ml of 0.1 M H₂O₂ was added. The reactor was hermetically sealed and placed on a magnetic stirrer located in front of the radiation source. During the irradiation process, nitrogen

was supplied to the reactor at a constant rate (10 ml/min), and the exiting gas mixture was sent to a flow meter to control the gas flow rate. Samples for analysis were taken into a 100 ml resealable gas pipette after it was washed for 20 minutes with nitrogen. The gas mixture was collected for 20 minutes.

The analysis of the gas mixture was carried out by gas chromatography using a "Кристалл 5000.1" chromatograph (Russia) applied chromatographic columns.

The productivity of molecular hydrogen generation was estimated by the formula:

$$w = \frac{C_{H_2} V_{g.v.} \cdot 6 \cdot 10^5}{\tau m_{ct} 22.4} [\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}], \quad (2)$$

where C_{H_2} is hydrogen concentration [%], $V_{g.v.}$ is gas vessel volume [ml], τ is gas collection time [min], m_{ct} is catalyst mass [g]

Aqueous solutions of carboxylic acids (HCOOH, H₂C₂O₄, citric, malic), hydrazine and sucrose were used as "sacrificial" reagents.

Results and discussion

Phase composition and optical properties

Table 1 presents the results of phase and elemental analysis of the composites. The main phases of ceramic matrices are following semiconductors Si₃N₄, TiN, Si₃Al₃O₃N₅, BN and VN, therefore the abbreviation of composites reflects the predominant phase SiN-SiC, TiN, SiAlON, BN and VN respectively. Table 1 also shows the results the iron concentration on the surface of the samples using elemental micro-X-ray spectral analysis. The highest iron content is observed in samples BN and VN, which is preferable for the photo-Fenton reaction. It has been found that composite granules are particles agglomerates of different shapes, consisting of small one (0.5-10 microns in size) and larger structures (20-40 microns). The metallic iron phase was distributed more uniformly over the surface of the BN composite [6].

Tabele 1

Phase composition and optical properties

Composition	Phases	w(Fe), %	E_g , eV	Semiconductor	Ref. E_g , eV
SiN-SiC	β -Si ₃ N ₄ , α -Fe, β -Si ₃ Al ₃ O ₃ N ₅ , SiC, FeSi	1.8–2.6	3.5, 2.6	β -Si ₃ N ₄ , SiC	4.0-4.5 [7] 2.4-3.0 [8]
TiN	TiN, β -Si ₃ N ₄ , α -Si ₃ N ₄ , α -Fe, FeSi/FeSi ₂	2.0–4.7	3.2	TiN	3.4 [9]
SiAlON	β -Si ₃ Al ₃ O ₃ N ₅ , β -Si ₃ N ₄ , α -Fe, FeSi/FeSi _{2y}	1.6–2.5	4.3	Si _{6-x} Al _x O _x N _{8-x}	2.3-5.3 [10]
BN	α -BN, α -Fe, FeB+Fe ₂ B	5–35	5.3, 3.8	α -BN, FeB	4.0-5.8 [11]
VN	VN, α -Fe, (V ₂ N)	15–19	5.4, 3.6	VN, V ₂ N	2.4 [12]

The optical properties of the composites are presented in Figure 1. It can be seen that diluting the charge with shungite leads to an increase in the degree of absorption and an expansion of the spectral region towards the far UV in the wavelength range 250–400 nm (SiN-SiC) compared to the spectrum of the SiAlON sample. This is due to the formation of the silicon carbide phase, which is consistent with the studies of the authors [13], who observed the absorption band of fine SiC powder in the region of 300-400 nm. The TiN com-

posite modified with a titanium additive is characterized by higher light absorption capacity in the UV and visible spectral region of 250–800 nm. The formation of the Ti-N bond promotes the absorption of visible radiation and explains the highest optical activity of the TiN composite in the visible region [14].

The correlation between the absorption coefficient $F(R) \cdot E$ and photon energy $h\nu$ for SiN-SiC, TiN and SiAlON, BN and VN composites is shown in Figure 1b. The obtained values of the band gap of the studied samples are presented in Table 1, where they are compared

with the literature values of E_g of semiconductors included in the ceramic matrix.

Comparing the obtained values of the band gap of the composites, we can emphasize that the SiN-SiC composite spectrum has a lower E_g value than the spectrum of the SiAlON composite. Sialon is a solid solution of variable composition $\text{Si}_{6-x}\text{Al}_x\text{O}_x\text{N}_{8-x}$, which is formed when Si is replaced by Al and N by O in β -silicon nitride. The SiN-SiC composite is the inclusion of a narrow-gap semiconductor SiC into its ceramic matrix, likewise the TiN composite, which has a value of $E_g = 3.3$ eV, comparable to n-type titanium nitride [15]. The main semiconductor phases of VN and BN composites have a wide band gap, close to dielectrics.

Boron nitride in the BN composite has an α modification with a hexagonal crystal structure. The band gap of α -BN was found to depend on the preparation method [12]. The calculated value of E_g is in agreement with the literature data for the BN composite synthesized by the SHS method. The spectrum of the BN composite also has an absorption band at 240–250 nm, related to the FeB phase ($E_g = 3.8$ eV), and in the spectrum of the VN composite there is an absorption band at 280–300 nm, characteristic of V_2N . It could be noticed that the band gap values of the semiconductors included in the ceramic matrix of the composites are lower than the photon energy of the UV radiation source (4.5 eV). This indicates the ability of the composites to exhibit photocatalytic activity in the UV range.

Figure 1 a) absorption spectra of composites b) dependence of the extinction coefficient $F(R) \cdot E$ on the energy of the absorbed photon $E(h\nu)$

Comparing estimation of the composite photocatalytic under UV and visible irradiation

To increase the activity of iron-ceramic composites and shift it to the visible light region, catalysts containing several semiconductors were synthesized (Table 1). It was of interest to carry out a comparing estimation of the photocatalytic activity of the original (SiAlON) and modified composites (SiN-SiC, TiN) in the process of generating H_2 from “sacrificial reagents” under UV and visible irradiation conditions. In addition,

the photocatalytic activity of iron-containing samples based on wide-gap semiconductors BN and VN was studied. Carboxylic acids ($\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$, HCOOH , malic acid), sucrose and hydrazine, which are oxidized under UV irradiation conditions to release H_2 , were used as “sacrificial” reagents. Table 2 shows the results of the performance composite estimation in the process of generating hydrogen from various “sacrificial” reagents depending on their concentration under conditions.

Table 2

Productivity ($\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{g}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$) of H_2 generation from solutions of “sacrificial” reagents under conditions of UV irradiation and visible light ($m_{\text{ct}} = 200$ mg; $V_{\text{sl}} = 20$ ml; $C(\text{H}_2\text{O}_2) = 0.001$ M; $t = 20$ min)

No	Solution systems	SiC	TiN	BN	VN
1	0.05 M $\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 / \text{UV}$	331	266	654	322
2	0.5 M $\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 / \text{UV}$	755	644	1200	756
3	0.5 M $\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4 / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 / \text{vis}$	660	190	1580	1070
4	0.1 M $\text{HCOOH} / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 / \text{UV}$	180	84	413	289
5	0.5 M $\text{HCOOH} / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 / \text{UV}$	541	236	393	314
6	0.5 M $\text{HCOOH} / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 / \text{vis}$	201	145	666	759
7	1.9 M $\text{HCOOH} / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 / \text{UV}$	1639	796	1134	1205
8	1.01 M $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7^* / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 / \text{UV}$	257	438	256	307
9	0.5 M $\text{C}_4\text{H}_6\text{O}_5^{2*} / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 / \text{UV}$	821	716	563	311
10	0.2 M $\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 / \text{UV}$	331	592	2488	2787
11	0.2 M $\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 / \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 / \text{vis}$	345	139	1964	1685
12	1% $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_{11}^{3*} \text{ pH } 2 / \text{UV}$	276	342	384	259
13	1% $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_{11}^{3*} \text{ pH } 2 / \text{vis}$	157	62	247	225
14	$\text{HCOOH} (0.5 \text{ M})$	386	228	315	623
15	0.5 M HCOOH			11	

The addition of H₂O₂ to the solution leads to the appearance of a photo-Fenton system, which generates a super-oxidant OH[•] radicals and promotes the oxidative destruction of carboxylic acids with the release of H₂. When oxalic acid is used in solution, a ferrioxalate photo-Fenton reaction occurs, increasing the efficiency of homogeneous photocatalysis and the formation of H₂. This is supported by the presence of CO₂ in the gas phase, the concentration of which increases with increasing amount of released H₂.

The photocatalytic activity of the SiN-SiC (620 μmol·h⁻¹·g⁻¹) and TiN (529 μmol·h⁻¹·g⁻¹) composites is more than twice that of the SiAlON composite (295 μmol·h⁻¹·g⁻¹). This indicates the participation in the photocatalytic process of SiC and TiN semiconductors, which have a narrower band gap than sialon. In the system H₂C₂O₄ is oxidized to CO₂ and H⁺ ions are reduced to H₂. Under the conditions of the photo-Fenton and ferrioxalate photocatalytic systems, the super-oxide radical O₂⁻ can be formed, which is able to reduce Fe(III) to Fe(II), promote the generation of H₂O₂ and hydroxyl radicals in radical chain photocatalytic reactions of photo-Fenton (equations 3-5) [16, 17]:

The highest productivity of H₂ production upon irradiation with visible light is observed from solutions of oxalic acid with the addition of H₂O₂ for all composites. Moreover, in the presence of BN and VN samples, the efficiency of H₂ release under visible light conditions is significantly higher than under UV irradiation (Table 2). This is due to the fact that in these systems the largest amount of photoactive ferrioxalate complex [Fe(C₂O₄)₃]³⁻ is formed, which undergoes photolysis in the radiation region of the LED lamp 400–500 nm and generates Fe²⁺ and hydroxyl radicals with a high quantum yield 1.24 (equations 6-9) [18]:

The high efficiency of BN and VN composites in homogeneous processes is explained by the increased Fe content (Table 1). It is important to note that most of the metallic iron in the catalysts remains in the ceramic matrix, so the efficiency of homogeneous photocatalytic systems does not change regardless of its leaching. In this case, the concentration of iron in the solution does not exceed 10–3 mg·l⁻¹, which is significantly lower than the maximum permissible concentration of iron (0.5–5 mg·l⁻¹) in water.

Conclusions

The production of iron-ceramic composites using SHS is the prospect method due to low energy cost, ease of use and one-step synthesis process. In addition, waste from the ferroalloy industry (Yurginsky Abrasive Plant, Russia) is used as feedstock. This approach is more economical and environmentally friendly compared to traditional synthesis methods that use commercial highly dispersed powders of boron, silicon and aluminum oxides.

The composites are active photocatalysts for the production of molecular hydrogen from organic substances both under UV and visible light conditions. The high activity of photocatalysts is due to the combination of semiconductor materials and metallic iron in a ceramic matrix. This probably makes it possible to combine heterogeneous and homogeneous (in the presence of H₂O₂) photocatalytic processes leading to synergistic effects. Thus, a homogeneous photo-Fenton system causes heterogeneous reactions involving semiconductors.

Oxalic acid and hydrazine are the most preferred sacrificial reagents (700 – 2000 μmol·h⁻¹·g⁻¹). It was found that the high productivity of VN and BN composites in the production of H₂ from H₂C₂O₄ is due to the high iron content and the formation in the solution of a photoactive ferrioxalate system with [Fe(C₂O₄)₃]³⁻ complexes, which undergoes photolysis in the radiation range of a visible light lamp (400–500 nm) and with a high quantum yield generates OH[•] radicals that oxidize organic compounds. The highest productivity of hydrogen production (1500–2800 μmol/h g) was achieved using a BN and hydrazine composite. In this case, heterogeneous photocatalysis plays a major role under UV irradiation.

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